

Optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian, Moving Mirror Problem and Two Conservation Laws

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Fermat's principle of least time may be used to calculate trajectories of light in various practical problems such as the reflection of light from both a stationary and moving mirror and refraction. In these problems, a result from Fermat's principle namely that light moves in a straight line is used and the problem becomes one of dealing with two straight lines namely an incident ray and a reflected or refracted ray and finding the reflected or refracted angle given the incident. There is no mention of conservation or momentum in such a scenario. For refraction, namely Snell's law, however one sees that the Fermat's result $\sin(A) n_1 = \sin(B) n_2$ where n_1 and n_2 are indices of refraction and A and B incident and refracted angles measured with respect to a normal is of the form of a conservation law of sorts namely equates two weighted x type projections. In fact the approach of minimizing time i.e. $dt/dx = 0$ for two rays each expressed in terms of $t = \text{distance}/\text{velocity}$ with distance being of the form $\sqrt{xx + yy}$ or $\sqrt{(L-x)(L-x) + yy}$ for example leads to $x/\sqrt{xx+yy}$ weighted terms being equated which is the form of a conservation law in the x direction.

The idea of conservation of momentum exists independent of Fermat's principle. In fact in (1) it is suggested that Snell's law may be derived using conservation of the x component of momentum instead of utilizing Fermat's principle. For the x component one would expect $p_1 \sin(A) = p_2 \sin(B)$. To link Snell's law to conservation of momentum, however, one may use another independent result namely $E=pc$. If one insists that for the refraction problem E remains constant and it is known that $c/n(i)$ is the speed in medium (i) (i.e. the definition of the index of refraction), then $p_{\text{vacuum}} \rightarrow p_{ni}$. Thus one may multiply Snell's law by p to obtain the conservation of momentum equation.

Furthermore there is an optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian formalism (2) which has been developed which makes use of the index of refraction and defines a "momentum" as n multiplied by a unit vector in the direction of a ray. Conservation i.e. Snell's law follows from this formalism which seems to be directly linked to ideas refraction.

In this note we consider the problem of light reflecting from a mirror moving in the negative y direction with a constant speed v . There is only one index of refraction in the problem as there is only one medium i.e. air and it may be set to 1. Fermat's principle may be used to minimize the time spent by the incident and reflected rays and to find a relationship between A and B the incident and reflected angles. Again there is a priori no conservation law or momentum in the picture. This exact calculation is performed in (3) and the result does not have the immediate form of an x axis projection conservation law i.e. it is $\sin(A) - \sin(B) = -v/c \sin(A+B)$.

Again based on independent arguments there should also be conservation of momentum in the x direction. Thus one knows $p(\text{incident})$ and A , and Fermat's minimum time principle gives B in terms of A and so one may ultimately calculate $p(\text{reflected})$ as well. It turns out that the moving mirror may be formulated in exactly the same way as a refraction problem if one chooses $1/(v \text{ relative } i)$ where $i = \text{incident, reflected}$ to be the indices of refraction. The index of refraction is chosen so that c/n is the velocity of light i.e. $\sin(A)/v(\text{relative } a) = \sin(B) / v(\text{relative } b)$. One may see the relationship with refraction by replacing $v(\text{relative})$ with c/n to obtain Snell's law. In such a case one again has conservation law namely the one used in (5) to equate

Fermat's principle to a hypothetical velocity but a second conservation law namely the conservation of the x component of momentum may be obtained by considering p_{initial} as given and $p_{\text{final}}/p_{\text{initial}} = v(\text{relative incident})/v(\text{relative reflected})$ following the idea of $E=pc$ with c and p changing so that E stays constant. Note in this case E and p for the incident and reflected rays differ. In fact $p_1 = p/v(\text{relative } a)$ so the so-called index of refraction is actually part of the momentum of the ray moving in air. $E=pc$ is only used as formalism. This is a different approach from using Lorentz transformations or (4) which considers changes in the wavelength after reflection to determine the ratio of $p(\text{initial})$ and $p(\text{final})$. The optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theory shows that ultimately a conserved quantity as a particular projection exists and so one may anticipate that this is directly linked to conservation of the same momentum projection if one is able to find an appropriate "index of refraction".

Optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian Theory

Fermat's principle of least time provides a direct relationship between A the angle of incidence and B the angle of reflection or refraction as measured with respect to a normal. This at first glance does not seem to be linked to a conservation law. The idea of conservation, however, appears because for reflection or refraction problems one considers incident light striking the mirror or medium at a point x (on the x axis), but uses the ray (hypotenuse) to calculate time. One varies hypotenuse = $\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$ with respect to x which yields a $\sin(A)$ (measured from the y axis) expression which is part of a projection. Given that $dt/dx = 0$ and there are two such hypotenuse pieces (incident and reflected/refracted) leading to an equation of the form of:

Weighted projection in the x direction 1 = weighted projection in the x direction 2 ((1))

((1)), however, is of the form of a conservation law even though the objective of Fermat's principle is only to find the reflected/refracted ray angle B in terms of the incident A . It is good, however, that a conservation type of law exists ((1)) because this may be directly linked to an independent second conservation law namely that of the x projection of momentum. To link ((1)) with conservation of momentum one may use:

$E=pc$ If c changes as in refraction to c/n then p changes to pn . ((2a))

This does not mean that E necessarily stays constant. For physical refraction it does, but for the moving mirror problem this is only a formalism. In particular the physical incident momentum is $p_1=p/(v \text{ relative } a)$. The so called index of refraction is part of the momentum value and p is a constant.

For refraction Snell's law yields: $n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B)$ so ((2)) indicates that:

$p_1 \sin(A) = p_2 \sin(B)$ ((2b))

Thus there are two conservation laws, but they are directly linked

The optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theory makes these ideas explicit (2). The optical Lagrangian is defined as: ($x_1=x$, $x_2=y$, $x_3=z$ and n = index of refraction)

$$L = n(x_1, x_2, x_3) \sqrt{1 + dx_1/dx_3 dx_1/dx_3 + dx_2/dx_3 dx_2/dx_3} \quad ((2c)) \quad \text{so}$$

$$p(i) = dL/d(dx(i)/dx_3) = n^2 dx(i)/dx_3 / \sqrt{1 + dx_1/dx_3 dx_1/dx_3 + dx_2/dx_3 dx_2/dx_3} \quad ((2d))$$

This is in the form of an (i)-projection angle which is linked to an (i) axis conservation law.

One may write a $p(i)$ for an incident ray and another for a reflected/refracted ray. Then:

$$dL/dx(x_i) - d/d(x_3) dL/dx(i) = 0 \quad \text{so} \quad dL/dx(i) = p(i) = \text{constant} \quad ((2e))$$

((2e)) leads directly to a conservation law if the same constant holds for the incident and reflected rays (see (2) for more details). This conservation law stands on its own (e.g. the hypothetical velocity conservation), but is also linked to conservation of momentum in the (i) direction e.g. along the mirror surface.)

One may define an optical Hamiltonian $H = p_1 dx_1/dx_3 + p_2 dx_2/dx_3 - L$ ((2f)) and Hamilton's equations will lead to the same conclusions.

Moving Mirror Problem

The above ideas seem to pertain to a problem with two indices of refraction i.e. refraction. A moving mirror problem, however, has only one index of refraction which may be taken to be 1. How does a conservation law appear in such a case? It seems that it follows from ((1)) i.e. a weighted average including an x projection divided by a hypotenuse appears leading again to a form $\sin(A)$ and $\sin(B)$. This may be seen explicitly for reflection from a mirror moving with constant v in the negative y direction as shown in (3). Their result after taking $d(\text{time})/dx$ is equivalent to:

$$\sin(A) / v(\text{relative } 1) = \sin(B) / v(\text{relative } 2) \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{Where } v(\text{relative } 1) = c - v \cos(A) \text{ and } v(\text{relative } 2) = c + v \cos(B) \quad ((3b))$$

One may note that in (3) Fermat's result is presented as $\sin(A) - \sin(B) = -v/c \sin(A+B)$ so it must be rearranged to yield ((3a)).

Thus we suggest that one may consider $1/v(\text{relative } i)$ as playing the role of an index of refraction. (3) takes a different point of view as they use Fermat's principle to find a relationship between angles A (incident) and B reflected, but then compares this relationship with results obtained by solving the moving mirror problem by using Lorentz transformations. Such an approach does bring out the conservation law which seems to be at work. ((3)) represents a

conservation of hypothetical velocity introduced in (5). There it is stated that there is a conserved hypothetical velocity in the x direction such that:

$$H \sin(A) = v(\text{relative } a) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = v(\text{relative } b) \quad ((4))$$

Given that one has ((3)) in the form of Snell's law if one makes the appropriate choice of index of refraction, one may link it to conservation of momentum in the x direction i.e.

$$p_1 \sin(A) = p_2 \sin(B) \quad ((5))$$

To do so one has to consider $p_1 = p/(v \text{ relative } a)$ and $p_2 = p / (v \text{ relative } b)$ with p being a constant. ((6)).

This follows from the idea of $E=pc$ with $c \rightarrow c/n$ and $p \rightarrow np$ as a formalism. Even though there is not an actual change in index of refraction, relative speeds of light with respect to the moving mirror change giving the semblance of two different media with different indices of refraction even in a reflection problem. (One should note that physically p_1 and p_2 have different energies because the actual p incorporates the so-called index of refraction $1/(v \text{ relative})$ while it does not in a refraction problem. (For example, light with a certain energy E may refract in a medium and then emerge back into air.)

The authors of (3) take the relationship of angles A and B found by Fermat's principle and then in (4) explicitly calculate how an incident wavelength changes by reflecting off a moving mirror. This leads to a relationship between $p(\text{incident}) / p(\text{reflected}) = \text{Function}(A, B)$, but we have shown in other notes that this result is compatible with ((5)). In fact, Fermat's principle result is directly linked to ((5)) if one uses the idea of $E=pc$ or $c \rightarrow c/n$ and $p \rightarrow np$ as a formalism.

Thus the main point we wish to make is that Fermat's principle for the moving mirror problem leads directly to a conservation equation which in turn is directly linked to conservation of momentum along the mirror surface.

Lorentz Transformations

One may note that given that the mirror moves in the negative y direction, momentum projections along the x direction do not transform under Lorentz transformations. In a moving frame in which the mirror is stationary there is conservation of momentum along the x direction so there should also be conservation of p_x in the lab frame.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that Fermat's minimal time principle in the case of two ray problems (reflection from a stationary and moving mirror, refraction) takes the form of a $\text{weight}(A) \sin(A) = \text{weight}(B) \sin(B)$ ((7)) which is equivalent to a conservation law. Furthermore this law represents projections along the x -axis and may be linked directly to conservation of momentum along this direction. This link follows directly in the refraction problem with $c \rightarrow c/n$ and $p \rightarrow np$ so that $E=pc$

remains constant. For reflection from a moving mirror there is only one index of refraction which may be taken to be 1. Fermat's principle, however, is of the form ((7)) so one may treat the weights as equivalent to indices of refraction.

In fact in the moving mirror problem they represent $1/v$ (relative). This first conservation law is equivalent to the hypothetical velocity approach introduced in (5).

((7)) is also linked to a second conservation namely conservation of momentum in the x direction.

References

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